

Role of Probiotics Application in Aquaculture

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Abstract: Aquaculture is the world's fastest growing food-producing sector. However, fish culture is currently suffering from the serious losses due to infectious diseases. As a result, probiotic use in aquaculture is rising in response to the need for environmentally friendly, sustainable aquaculture. Probiotic is a healthy substitute that can be utilized to increase aquaculture productivity in a sustainable manner. Their application has various benefits in aquaculture production as improves growth performance, enhance feed utilization, enhance the immune defense against the pathogens, improves disease resistance, improves water quality, enhance stress tolerance capacity. Probiotic use in aquaculture can therefore be utilized at the farm level to improve the species' economic performance.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, Aquaculture is the world's fastest-growing food production sector. World aquaculture production reached 130.9 million tonnes in 2022 of these Asia contributing 91.4 %. World aquaculture has grown tremendously during last 20 years from a production about 43.4 million tonnes in 2002 to 130.9 million tonnes by 2022. The demand for the consumption of fish is increasing day by day. So, with increase in intensification and commercialization of aquaculture production come many challenges such as combating diseases, broodstock improvement, development of appropriate feedstuff, hatchery and grow-out technology as well as water quality management. Of these, disease outbreaks are one of the important problems that affect aquaculture production, suppressing both economic and social development in many countries. According to a number of earlier studies (Kim and Austin, 2006; Mohideen *et al.*, 2010; Wang and Gu, 2010), probiotic supplementation can lower disease outbreaks by strengthening fish and shrimp's immune systems and can also lower culture expenses by promoting fish growth and feed efficiency. Additionally, probiotics can improve animal physiology, which in turn can improve water quality by

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